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FOR MOBILE RADIO COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS OVER NAKAGAMI FADING CHANNEL

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ABSTRACT

Diversity combining is a technique in wireless network that uses multiple antenna system to improve the quality of radio signal. Mobile radio system suffers multipath propagation due to signal obstruction in the channel. A new hybridized diversity combining scheme consisting of Equal Gain Combining (EGC) and Maximal Ratio Combining (MRC) was proposed in this paper. The performance of the hybrid model was evaluated using Outage Probability (P_{out}) and Processing time (P_t) at different Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and Signal Paths ($L=2,3$) for 4-QAM and 8-QAM Modulation Schemes. A mathematical expression for the hybrid EGC-MRC was realized using the Probability Density Function (PDF) of the Nakagami fading channel. MATLAB R2015b software was used for the model simulation. The result shows that hybrid EGC-MRC outperforms the standalone EGC and MRC schemes by having lower P_{out} and P_t values. Hence, hybrid EGC-MRC exhibits enhanced potentials to mitigate multipath propagation at reduced system complexity.

KEYWORDS

Equal Gain Combining (EGC), Nakagami, Outage Probability, Processing Time, Multipath, Hybrid

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USING SOCIAL MEDIA AS A TOOL FOR PROMOTING FESTIVAL TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

The impact of social media on Tourism has been one of the main topics in tourism research. Many studies discuss and analyze the impact of social media on Tourism. However, less research studied on the impact of social media on specific, like festivals tourism. Festival make people united and the experiences of those participating in festivals can have a significant influence on others and social media provides the perfect channel for sharing their experiences.

This research focused on social media factors that influenced visitors in the festival tourism. The study was designed to explore how social media factors impact to festival tourism. The structured interview was conducted to confirm social media factors from secondary data. The results show that social media better use as a search engine tools. For future research it is suggested to conduct quantitative survey to confirm these social media factors which analyzed by this study.

KEYWORDS

Social media, Festival, tourism, Festival tourism, eWOM

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WEB-BASED LEARNING IN PERIODS OF CRISIS: REFLECTIONS ON THE IMPACT OF COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

Education systems and its actors are generally responding to quarantine and large-scale shutdown (partial) of cities with a sudden shift to Web-Based Learning. However, given that a pandemic of this nature and scale is novel, there is a knowledge gap as to how teachers and learners should respond to the shift, and what the likely impact and the key considerations should be. This study aims to extrapolate and theorize from the existing knowledgebase about the use of Web-Based Learning, as well as from an expert and practitioner wisdom and experience, to offer high-level guidance for policymakers and education system actors that are forced to make decisions in fast-moving and very challenging circumstances with little guidance or relevant experience. It is an early attempt at theorizing the impact of the pandemic on two key actors (Learners and Teachers) and one interface (Content), all across eight dimensions of learning. The analysis is based on Khan's (2001) dimension of Web-Based Learning and Anderson's (2011) Model of Online Learning. Overall, we posit based on experience and practice, that the pandemic has delivered severe shocks to both the demand and supply side of Web-Based Learning, with Learners, Teachers, and Content all significantly affected. While we hypothesize a general drop in the quality of teaching and learning in the short run, we expect the opposite to be the case in the long run, when the demand and supply side self-correct, albeit guided by strong government and market institutions.

KEYWORDS

Web-Based Learning, COVID-19, Learners

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